

PROBLEMS OF TRANSCRIPTION AND TRANSLITERATION OF PERSONAL NAMES IN MODERN ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article analyzes the problems, technologies, forms of transcription and transliteration of personal names in modern English.

Keywords: Transcription, transliteration, modern English, language, neologism.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that every language changes and forms in its own way. At any time, language can leave its traces in history. Language is a means of communication between individuals, and culture is a certain level of society development.

The mutual interest of communication between people leads to the fact that new words gradually or fully penetrate the everyday vocabulary of a person. Neologisms can last a long time in the language or they may completely disappear. Today in the world there are many changes of technical, economic, state-legal, and public nature. It is thanks to these changes in the language system that words are formed and outdated views are replaced¹⁷.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Linguistics has a great number of various methods nowadays. but we have used definite ones. The analysis of theoretical and supporting data comprise the usage of such methods as comparative method, analytical method, linguistic observation and generalization.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the analysis it was revealed that among the lexical units used by J. Tolkien to denote invented objects and subjects of the magical world, the most demanded are the structures formed by the way:

1) in the translation of the work “The Lord of the rings” into russian for A.b. Kistyakovsky, a functional replacement, as for the author’s new formations it is not at all easy to find analogies in the translating language. The second most important for this translator is the tracing, then the mixed translation;

2) in the translation of the work “The Lord of the rings” into russian for v.s.

¹⁷ B.A Serebrennikov, The role of the human factor in the language: Language and the picture of the world, Moscow: Science, pp. 80, 2018.

Muravyov, the most productive method of translation prevails - a functional replacement. And, also the necessary reception for the transfer of neologisms, and tracing. Advantages of the method of tracing are the brevity and uncomplicated equivalence invented with its help and its absolute correlation with a certain word. In third place is the translation of occasionalism¹⁸.

A study of author neologisms by Joan K. Rowling made it possible to discover the translation strategies that translators used, namely:

in the translation of the work "Harry Potter" into the Russian language of the translator I.M. Oransky, the reception of a functional replacement predominates. Then transliteration and transcription. Transcribed names do not have any semantic load, as hints, allusions and associations that are significant for children, on which this work of art is traced, disappear;

1) in the translation of the work "Harry Potter" into the Russian language of the translator M.V. Spivak, mainly, the predominantly tracing. In second place is transcription, then abbreviation.

An important goal of the translator is to familiarize readers who do not know a foreign language with the text, in preserving the traditional color, author neologisms, structure and style of the author writing. The translator is not able to completely avoid language contradictions, but he needs to know about them and take them into account.

Researchers come to the conclusion that the formation of new words at the time of their detection follows some stages. They do not agree on the problem of interim comparability of neologisms. Therefore, it is worth remembering that new words can be divided into two groups: linguistic and authorial groups. Their ways of forming and interacting with each other are slightly different. Linguistic neologisms are words and phrases that have only arisen in the language and are used to determine the newest or already familiar object and point of view. The person who owns this language is understood as the linguistic neologism, as the last, a new word that has a peculiar spiritual structure.

A.M. Alekseeva believes that the borrowing of English continues to increase only to a small extent, than it was in the Middle Ages and the Renaissance. Then new words appeared in different areas of life in a short time. From the "receiving" language, English turns into a "giving" language. This is because the English language won the status of Lingua franca ("Frankish language" - the language used as a means of interethnic communication in a certain field of activity) of the 20th century. But, despite the fact that borrowings contain only 7.5% of the total number of neologisms and are on the periphery

¹⁸ E.V. Breus, Theory and practice of translation from English, Moscow: Publishing house URAO, pp. 283, 2016.

of the lexical system, their analysis is absolutely important, since without this layer one can not imagine a full body of new vocabulary¹⁹.

CONCLUSION

The translator can interpret the “inner form” of the new word very carefully and only in those cases when there is absolute certainty in accordance with the received translation. Among the encountered linguistic means, it is necessary to find equivalents that will be appropriate to the original. Important conditions for obtaining conformity in the translation of author’s neologisms of English fiction are:

1. Knowledge of the features of the interaction of a new word with the context, as well as the main cases of using different structural and semantic types of neologisms.

2. Knowledge of the main ways of translating the author’s neologisms and the ability to correctly find the equivalent Russian version of the corresponding English neologism.

3. The ability to find and correctly use the most appropriate way of creating a new correspondence for the translation of the author’s neologism, which does not have a Russian equivalent or that reflects a specific phenomenon that is absent in our reality.

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¹⁹ I.S. Alekseeva, Introduction to translation studies, St. Petersburg: The Change, pp. 263, 2004.

